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**РОЗВИТОК ОБЛІКУ, АУДИТУ ТА ОПОДАТКУВАННЯ
В УМОВАХ ІННОВАЦІЙНОЇ ТРАНСФОРМАЦІЇ
СОЦІАЛЬНО-ЕКОНОМІЧНИХ СИСТЕМ**

**DEVELOPMENT OF ACCOUNTING, AUDIT, AND TAXATION
IN THE CONDITIONS OF INNOVATIVE TRANSFORMATION
OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC SYSTEMS**

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PERSPECTIVES USING CRYPTOGRAPHY TOOLS PYTHON FOR BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGIES IN FINANCE TRANSACTION

The impetuous development of modern computer equipment and information technology opens up new prospects for their application in all economic sectors, to improve the efficiency of the economic management processes and financial transactions. Wherein, along with the information technology advantages, the possible emergence of risks in economical various sectors, in particular in finance, also deserves attention. In this area of economics noticeable, the transformation prevalence trend of the role and form money, the latest digital technologies spread. The intensification of the digital high-tech innovative technologies introduced in the financial sector has also led to the many risks' emergence, among which transaction security is actuality. In transactions, traditional electronic databases are mainly used which provide the ability and means to create, edit, and delete data at any time. From

a security viewpoint, access to such databases carried out mainly using two or three user identification levels. However, even such measures do not always guarantee the complete financial transactions' security, due to the possible unauthorized access of unauthorized persons to confidential information stored in an electronic database. In the event of unauthorized access to confidential financial information in the database, an attacker can gain opportunities to correct and delete information, that is, to conduct financial transactions in real-time and even in the past. Tracking such unauthorized intrusions into the database is not always possible for the security service, especially in cases when highly qualified hackers carry out such actions.

A scientific publications' analysis has shown that researchers are not enough attention devoted to the perspective disclosure for using Python cryptography in blockchain finance technologies. The overwhelming publications' majority is devoted to disclosing the benefits and general problems of using blockchain technologies in economics. In particular, A. Zhmurkevych and R. Vakulin [1] showed the general functioning principles and application of blockchain technologies. M. Raikwar, D. Gligoroski and K. Kralevska [2] identified a cryptographic concepts list that is not yet been applied but has great potential for improving current blockchain solutions. Researchers J. Varma [3] showed the advantages and prospects of using blockchain technology in micro-credit and insurance to increase the financial availability of the population. A. Guerrero-Sanchez with co-authors [4] proposed a methodology for protecting the integrity and availability of blockchain technology data with the cryptographic tools' introduction DES, DES-X, AES. P. Khandelwal, S. Patil, and D. Reddy [5] disclosed the advantages of using the hashing mechanism in blockchain technology to ensure transaction security. L. Er-Rajy with co-authors [6] showed the danger of possible attacks ways using powerful computers for unauthorized access to databases that operate based on blockchain technologies.

In the article, we set our task to show the prospects and advantages of using ways Python cryptography tools to ensure the security of the use of blockchain technologies in financial transactions. Blockchain technologies for creating databases, which also called distributed ledger technology (DLT), are safer compared to conventional database technologies since they provide for the use of information chain blocks consisting. Each block (records in the distributed ledger) can store information about several transactions. Each subsequent block has a link to the previous one on this principle created an unbroken chain. The blocks store records of subjects, time, and transaction date. Registries with data are stored not in one server (in comparison with conventional databases), but on several network computers participants, where they are constantly updated through an Internet connection. In this case, blocks cannot be changed or deleted; they can only add new ones. Therefore, in the blockchain, registries with data in asset transactions are almost impossible to forge, because this will require corrections on all the network participants' computers.

In the conventional databases, the responsibility for security rested with the administrators, and when using blockchain technologies, protection for information loss and blockchain transactions the "miners" provide. The miner's number in the network can be unlimited and the more there are, the transaction is more reliable. In

order to improve transaction security in the blockchain technology uses various means, for example, caching and cryptography.

As a study result of the above problems, we concluded that the most promising for ensuring the security of financial transactions are cryptography tools provided in the Python programming environment. Among distributed software for cryptography data in the Python environments are the elementary ones like “PyCrypto” (a kind of “PyCryptodome”) and “Cryptography”.

A “PyCrypto” add-software is intend for use in dynamic modules for data cryptography. We believe, among the proposed modules, perspectives for the implementation of cryptography of data in financial transactions is the RSA module, with private and public keys, which provide increased security of data encryption. In the RSA module using the “ExportKey” method is generates an access code to the RSA key, which is used by the PKCS standard to create the private key encryption scheme. Based on the private key, is to create the public key by the “Publickey” module. Wherein, "nonce" generates an arbitrary random or pseudo-random number for the public key. The user gains access to the encrypted transaction data only if the file is open in binary mode and the private access key is successfully import, by transferring the previously generated access code. A public key and the file remainder is a read based on a correctly entered private key. The information is display on the screen after decrypting the session key and transaction data.

Another software application in the Python environment is “Cryptography”, which is also securing capable data encryption. The “Fernet” module used in it implements a simple authentication scheme and symmetric data encryption algorithm. The rotation key through “MultiFernet” provides access to encrypted data and is in the form of a random bytes string. Such a key is dynamic since it is generate by the “Generate_key” method each time. Due to its dynamism, such a key can be consider as the first authentication level, which makes it much more difficult for an attacker to guess a key. Based on this key, strong cipher models are create, which are used by the “Encrypt” and ”Decrypt” methods to appropriately encrypt and decrypt sensitive transaction data.

Based on the above material, it can be note that the advantages of using “PyCrypto” and “Cryptography” with multilevel authentication of miners to ensure the security of the use of blockchain technologies in financial transactions are obvious. The indicated advantages of these additional software applications in the Python programming environment can be use in design the government programs and strategies of applying complex blockchain technologies in various economic sectors, in particular, to ensure a high-security level of financial transactions.

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